

Optimizing bridges modelling through visual programming

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Abstract

Various engineering fields have significantly advanced because of the use of visual programming and Building Information Modeling (BIM). In this study, we concentrate on using visual programming tools to improve the bridge modeling procedure and deal with problems caused by traditional approaches.

The main issue raised in this thesis is the limits of conventional bridge modeling methods that limit effective structural analysis and design. The objective is to fully utilize visual programming's ability to transform the bridge modeling procedure and speed up.

The goals of this study are addressed by combining qualitative and quantitative research techniques. We undertake evaluations to comprehend the current state-of-the-art in bridge modeling and the possible advantages of visual programming. To acquire insightful information from actual bridge projects and enable a thorough assessment of the suggested technique, case studies, and expert interviews are also used.

The findings of this study indicate how visual programming has enormous potential for improving bridge models. A Dynamo script may be used to generate the complete bridge in a fraction of the time needed by human techniques, cutting the modeling process from weeks

to just a few seconds. This quick generation makes it possible to make quick changes to the bridge design, including adjusting the span and pier height. Additionally, the use of visual programming speeds up the structural analysis procedure, enabling designers to choose e.g., the best concrete girder beam for a concrete bridge with confidence.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/19eCan3UryQ>

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